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An Observational Study Between *Sattvabala* And Stress Coping Capability Among IT Professionals

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Abstract

Background : According to Ayurvedic science, to assess the mental status of an individual, one need to understand his *Sattva* and its strength. The systemic and holistic approach is provided by the *Sattvabala* to understand a person adequately. To know the stress coping capability factor of IT professionals, examination of *Sattvabala* from Ayurveda Context will prove a definite useful tool.

Aim : To examine the correlation between *Sattva Bala* and stress coping capability among IT professionals.

Methodology- Descriptive observational research study with sample size 120, selfmade *Sattvabala* questionnaire and stress coping capability scale was used, percentage and pearson correlation coefficient was used for data analysis.

Result : *Sattvabala* and stress coping capability are highly correlated with each other.

Conclusion : To know the stress coping capability factor of IT professionals, examination of *Sattvabala* from Ayurveda Context will prove a definite useful tool.

Keywords: Mental Health, Occupational Stress, Stress Coping Capability, *Sattvabala*.

Introduction:

An essential branch of medicine is Ayurveda. It is essentially different from contemporary medical science. *Ayurveda* takes a comprehensive approach to medical science. It covers disease management as well as disease prevention and maintaining the health of the well^[1]. To prevent illness and prolong life, as well as to get rid of bodily malfunction. Adhering to this proverb, all authors of traditional *Ayurvedic* texts. An

individual can be called *Swastha* (healthy) when his *Daihika* constitution of *Dosha*, *Dhatu*, *Mala* and *Agni* are in equilibrium while *Atma* and *Mana* should be *Prasanna*. *Sushruta's* notion of "*Swastha*" emphasizes the mental, emotional, and physical health of people.^[2,3] *Mann* serves as the faculty's regulator and key component. While *Acharya Sushruta* does not specifically address *Sattva*, he does discuss the three attributes of humans based on their *Rajas*, *Tamas*, and *Sattva*

status. The body remains in a healthy state when these are in equilibrium. The ratio of *Tamas*, *Raja*, and *Sattva* differs from person to person. The people are classified as *Rajasika* (the superiority of *Rajas*), *Tamasika* (the superiority of *Tamas*) and *Sattvik* (the superiority of *Sattva*) based on the predominance of Guna^[4].

Ayurveda considers *Sattva* (mind) to be one of the three pillars (*Tridand*) on which life depends. They were always associated with mental attributes and identified in tandem with physical cues and symptoms. According to the Indian medical system, maintaining positive well-being can be achieved through understanding *Sattva* and its state. The *Sattva* is an prime entity, who creates the connection between the body and soul necessary for the proper operation of the *Indriya* (sensory organs). A person's adequate state of well-being is provided by *Sattvabala*, or "status/strength of mind," which offers a systemic and comprehensive approach to understanding an individual^[5].

Starting from 1946, the World health Organization has consistently highlighted the significance of wellness in defining mental health. The Information Technology (IT) Industry is one of the fastest growing industries in India employing nearly four million jobs. It is the most coveted one in modern India, and the most brilliant section of the youth are going for it. Some identified the key factors at the workplace which generate stress among IT personnel. It was suggested that factors which generate stress be grouped into 4 broad categories as^[6] -

- Lack of career advancement related to the problem of high rate of employee turnover.
- Work overload resulting in spillover of workload at home and guilt and dissatisfaction for being less attentive to family.
- Risk taking and decision making consisting of fear of making mistakes and Employee morale and organizational culture related to a lack of participation indecisions affecting their work.

- Undue blame for machine failure and difficulty in team work considering the noninvolved nature of work.
- In a study on Work Stress among Information Systems Professionals it was found that employees reported the commonly experienced feelings such as frustration, pride in accomplishments, being overwhelmed, anxiety and common stress symptoms decrease in energy, anxiety, muscle tension, headache, stomach upset, negative thinking and insomnia. The IT professionals are characterized with long working hours, tight schedules, high competition, continuous viewing of Visual Display Unit (VDU) etc., that are increasing the occupational stress and putting the health of them in danger. Approximately 75%- 80% of working professionals in India complain that they are experiencing stress and their organizations don't have any programmes to manage and handle stress at work. to know the stress coping capability factor of IT professionals, examination of *Sattvabala* from *Ayurveda* Context will prove a definite useful tool.

NHS Health Scotland describes good mental health as a "basic component of positive health and well-being. It is necessary to help us manage our lives successfully, and provide us with the emotional and spiritual resilience to allow us to enjoy life and cope with distress and disappointment^[7]."

Rationale of the study:

Assessment of *Sattvabala* is very important to know the one's mind strength. By assessing *Sattvabala*, we can assess stress coping capability of that person. It is helpful to find out the ways to treat that person's acute and chronic stress. Considering the IT Professionals here, this correlational study will be helpful to explore their *Sattvabala* status and capability of stress coping behavior. To deal with their mental health, this concept will be surely useful to physician in treating patient's psychological issues. Also, for

promotion of mental health, we can plan use of *Achar-Rasayana*, Yoga and *Sattvavajaya Chikitsa* according to patient's *Sattvabala*. Considering the above facts, the present study takes a holistic view of personhood. This has been planned to study the *Ayurvedic* term *Sattabala*, stress coping capability and find their relationship among Information technology professionals.

Research Question: Is there any correlation between *Sattva Bala* and stress coping capability among IT professionals?

Aim: To examine the correlation between *Sattva Bala* and stress coping capability among IT professionals.

Objectives: To assess and compare *Sattva Bala* and stress coping capacity among IT professionals and to find correlation between them.

Literature review of *Sattva Bala*:

Sattva has been regarded as the essential constituent of life and that it has been recognized as one of the chief determinants of human personality. *Sattva* is called *Mann* and it regulates the body because of its association with the soul. Depending upon its strength, it is of three types i.e., *Pravara*, *Madhyama* and *Avara*. *Acharya Charaka* has described *Dashavidha Pariksha* (tenfold examination) among which *Sattva Pariksha* (examination of the mind) has its own importance^[8,9,10,11] *Sushruta Samhita* has explained *Sattva* as the capacity of *Manas* which does not cause frustration at times of emotional turmoil. *Dalhana* has commented *Sattva* as *Manobala*, wherein the persons with *Satwa Guna* predominance will have *Uttama Manobala*, those with *Rajoguna* predominance will have *Madhyama Manobala* and persons with predominance of *Tamoguna* will have *Manodourbalya*. *Acharya Susruta* does not

mention *Sattva* separately but he explained the three qualities of individuals according to the status of *Sattva*, *Rajas* and *Tamas*. Equilibrium of these maintains the healthy state of the body. Proportion of *Sattva*, *Raja* and *Tamas* varies from person to person.

On the basis of predominance of *Guna* the individuals are said to be *Rajasika* (superiority of *Rajas*), *Tamasika* (superiority of *Tamas*) and *Sattvik* (superiority of *Sattva*). The person endowed with superiority of *Sattva* does not frustrate at times of distress and overcome panic situations because of his self-restraint and firmness. The person with the superiority of *Rajo Guna* can overcome problems by getting appreciation and motivation from others. The person with the superiority of *Tamo Guna* cannot tolerate any type of regret or penitence and they cannot overcome these situations. *Kapha Prakriti* individuals *Sattvawaan Asthey* are calm, non-aggressive, delicate, stable minded and have pleasing faces. They are blessed with steady thoughts, steady determination, excellent tolerance, good memory, and concentration power. Depending on the strength of *Manas*, *Charaka Samhita* describes the following qualities to assess the *Sattvbala*^[12,13]

- *Smruti*- Is the ability to recollect the objects of previous experience.
- *Bhakti*- Devotion
- *Krutajnata*- Intellectual, wise learned clever discriminator.
- *Shuchi*- Clean, pure, hygiene
- *Mahotsaha*- Good energy
- *Daksha*- Able, expert, clever, skillful
- *Dheera*- Brave, bold, courageous
- *Samara Vikranta Yodhinaha*- Powerful, victorious
- *Tyakta Vishada*- Devoid of sadness, dejection, grief, sorrow *Suvyavasthita Gati* and *Gambheera Buddhi Chesta*- Properly organized body language, intellect and behavior.

These properties are very much similar to the stress coping capability attribute of the person.

Literature review of stress coping capacity:

- Stress-it is a type of psychological strain that influences a person's attitude and conduct and is viewed as a burden. Stressors that might lead to such low moods can come from life transitions, family dynamics, the environment and nature of one's work and a variety of personal relationships. [14,15] Just like a stress may have varied effects on individual workers, the magnitude a IT professional perceives and the associated coping behavior may be varied as well.
- Coping- it is defined as the thoughts and behaviors mobilized to manage internal and external stressful situations. It is a term used distinctively for conscious and voluntary mobilization of acts, different from 'defense mechanisms' that are subconscious or unconscious adaptive responses, both of which aim to reduce or tolerate stress. Coping usually involves adjusting to or tolerating negative events or realities while you try to keep your positive self-image and emotional equilibrium. Coping occurs in the context of life changes that are perceived to be stressful. Adjusting to novel demands, or stresses, is part of coping. This calls for exerting more effort and energy than what is required for day-to-day living. Long-term exertion can raise stress-related hormone levels, which can lead to eventual physical deterioration and disease.
- Coping capability – It is one of the prime factors in the process of stress coping. [16] There are problem-focus and emotion-focus approaches to counter the stress. Problem-focus approach could be more effective in helping victim to solve the problems associated with stress than the emotion-focus [17,18,19].
- Stress coping capability- The ability to identify and accept stress in our life, as well as its cause and effects, is known as

coping with stress. It involves the capacity to manage the source of stress as well as take action to lessen or eliminate it. In order to perform successfully in a variety of contexts, this skill also entails managing fear and other challenging emotions as well as our comprehension of our feelings and responses to conflict. This ability gives us the resilience to deal with the surrounding emotions, confront stressful, unpredictable, and conflicting situations, and seek out the most advantageous alternatives [20].

Coping is generally categorized into four major categories which are :

1. Problem-focused- it addresses the problem causing the distress: Examples of this style include active coping, planning, restraint coping, and suppression of competing activities.
2. Emotion-focused - it aims to reduce the negative emotions associated with the problem: Examples of this style include positive reframing, acceptance, turning to religion, and humor.
3. Meaning-focused, in which an individual uses cognitive strategies to derive and manage the meaning of the situation
4. Social coping (support-seeking) in which an individual reduces stress by seeking emotional or instrumental support from their community.

Material and Methods:

- This is a descriptive observational research study with survey mode.
- Literary review of the *Sattvabala* and stress coping capacity were done from Ayurveda classical Context, scientific journals, libraries and various manuals of the IT companies.
- Total 120 subjects from the information technology field between the age group

21 to 50 from different region of India were included in this study.

- We have interviewed participants for collecting information relating to the present research with Google form and telephonically.
- we adopted a questionnaire as an instrument for the study. Self-made questionnaires were used for the assessment of *Sattvabala* comprising 36 items with 5 alternatives as- a) Better than others, b) same as others, c) Uncertain, d) Poor and e) very poor. On the basis of total scoring, *Sattvabala* of the subject has been assessed.
- For the assessment of stress coping capability, 'Coping Scale' developed by Hamby, Grych, & Banyard was used. This coping questionnaire assesses cognitive, emotional, and behavioral methods of dealing with problems. Scoring: Each answer category was assigned a value from 4 to 1. Higher scores indicate higher levels of stress coping capability. Total score (52) was categorized as- 1. Excellent = (36-52), 2. Medium= (1-35), 3. low= (0-20)^[21].

Data Analysis:

Percentages and the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient test were used for the data analysis. The Pearson's Correlation coefficient was used to describe the relationship between *Sattvabala* and stress coping capability among Information technology professionals.

Observations and Result:

- Out of total 120 IT professionals, 55% were male and 45% were females.
- 39% participants were from joint family and 61% were from nuclear family.
- 26%, 18%, 16% and 40% participants were having *Vishamagni*, *Tikshagni*, *Mandagni* and *Samagni* respectively.
- 34%, 33% and 33% participants were having *Krura*, *Mrudu* and *Madhyam Koshta* respectively.

- 41% were non vegetarian and 59% were vegetarian.
- 15%, 30%, 32% and 40% participants were having *Vatapittaj*, *Vatakaphaja*, *Pittakaphaja* and *Kaphapittaj Sharir Prakriti* respectively.
- 31%, 31% and 38% were having *Rajtamsik*, *Tamarajsik* and *Sattvarajsik* respectively.
- 25%, 53% and 22% were having *Pravara*, *Madhyama* and *Avara Sattvabala* respectively.
- 27%, 52% and 21% were having high, average and low stress coping capability.
- Pearson correlation coefficient between *Sattvabala* and stress coping capability is - **0.9256**. So, they are highly correlated with each other.

Chart .1: Correlation between *Sattvabala* and stress coping capability among IT professionals.

Conclusion-

- From the above research study, it can be concluded that as *Sattvabala* and stress coping capability are highly significantly correlated with each other, to know the stress coping capability factor of IT professionals, examination of *Sattvabala* from *Ayurveda* Context will prove a definite useful tool.
- Today we live in a very turbulent world, where breaking of law, distortion, violence, cheating, terrorization and dishonesty by students have become socially and morally acceptable. The superiority of *Sattva* is essential to be mentally and physically healthy. *Ayurveda Sattvavajay* concept,

- *Ayurveda Medhya* (brain booster) drugs, *Achar Rasayan, Sadvriitta* (*Ayurveda* codes and conducts) can be used to improve the *Madhyam* and *Avara Sattvabala* of the IT Professionals. This will improve their stress coping capability and surely helpful to achieve their life goals.
- More research in this topic is needed

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